

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CARBOXYMETHYL ASSAM BORA RICE STARCH COATED SPIONS FOR TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

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INTRODUCTION :

Carboxymethyl Assam Bora rice starch-coated superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (CM-ABRS SPIONs) were synthesized using a co-precipitation technique, with particle size regulation achieved through high-energy homogenization. Key processing parameters—including polymer concentration, homogenization speed, and the number of homogenization cycles—were systematically optimized based on the Z-average (mean particle size) and polydispersity index (PDI) of the CM-ABRS SPIONs. The optimized nanoparticles were thoroughly characterized in terms of particle size, surface morphology, zeta potential, chemical bonding, crystallinity, magnetic behavior, and their responsiveness to an external magnetic field for targeted delivery applications. To simulate magnetic drug targeting (MDT), an *in vitro* localization study was conducted using CM-ABRS SPIONs suspended in a medium containing FITC (Fluorescein isothiocyanate)-labeled red blood cells at a hematocrit level of 45% (v/v). This experiment was performed in a square glass capillary channel ($500 \times 500 \mu\text{m}^2$ cross-sectional area). The aggregation behavior of the CM-ABRS SPIONs over a time span of 0 to 600 seconds revealed a

correlation between nanoparticle clustering and the duration of magnetic field exposure. These findings offer valuable insights for the development and optimization of magnetically guided targeted drug delivery platforms.

Conventional cancer treatments often face significant challenges due to non-specific drug targeting, rapid drug release, and unintended damage to healthy tissues (Langer, 1998). To address these issues, nanoparticle (NP)-based drug delivery systems—particularly those utilizing targeted nanoparticles—have emerged as a promising alternative. These systems have the potential to enhance therapeutic outcomes by reducing the side effects associated with high drug dosages (Douziech-Eyrolles et al., 2007). Their adaptability for both therapeutic and diagnostic (theranostic) applications positions them as valuable tools in managing various health conditions (Klostergaard and Seeney, 2012). Such dual-function systems are believed to accelerate drug discovery processes, improve disease control, minimize dosing frequency and associated risks, and potentially reduce treatment costs. Especially in oncology, multifunctional targeted nanoparticles have gained attention for their ability to selectively deliver therapeutic agents to tumor sites while minimizing systemic toxicity (Klostergaard and Seeney, 2012). Among these systems, magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) stand out due to their responsiveness to external magnetic fields, which enables controlled and site-specific drug delivery. MNPs are typically composed of magnetic elements like iron (Fe), cobalt (Co), nickel (Ni), and manganese (Mn) (Park et al., 2000; Puntès et al., 2001), as well as bimetallic structures such as CoPt_3 , FePt, and FeZn (Grasset et al., 2002; Shevchenko et al., 2002; Sun et al., 2000). However, MNPs containing Co, Ni, and Mn have been associated with toxicity concerns, limiting their clinical applications unless further modifications are implemented (Dobson, 2007). In contrast, superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) are considered safer and more biocompatible, making them better suited for medical use (Weissleder et al., 1989). Commonly used forms, such as magnetite (Fe_3O_4) and maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), demonstrate superparamagnetic properties when their core size is reduced to 20 nm or smaller (Frey et al., 2009; Teja and Koh, 2009). Unlike paramagnetic materials, SPIONs exhibit no residual magnetism once the external magnetic field is removed, which is a critical feature for in vivo applications (Teja and Koh, 2009).

Among various stabilizing agents, starch has garnered considerable interest from researchers due to its non-toxic nature, widespread availability, biocompatibility, and biodegradability (Araújo et

al., 2004; Marques et al., 2002). However, the application of native starch in targeted drug delivery systems is limited by several inherent drawbacks. These include low solubility in cold water, a tendency to retrograde, inadequate powder flow, rapid drug release (burst effect), and high viscosity upon gelatinization (Delval et al., 2004; Santander-Ortega et al., 2010; Simi & Abraham, 2007). To enhance its performance and address these limitations, chemical modification of starch is often necessary. One such derivative, **carboxymethyl starch (CMS)**, has shown promise in overcoming these issues. CMS is particularly useful in drug delivery systems due to its ability to interact with drugs via electrostatic forces, facilitating drug encapsulation (Bagalkot et al., 2006; Mallick et al., 2016b; Syed et al., 2013). The presence of negatively charged carboxymethyl groups ($-\text{CH}_2\text{COO}^-$) in CMS not only improves drug loading efficiency but also contributes to its "stealth" properties. These characteristics help prolong the circulation time of drug-loaded nanoparticles in the bloodstream, enhance targeting efficiency, and support the delivery of hydrophilic drugs to specific sites within the body (Chang et al., 2010).

MATERIALS AND METHODS :

1) Materials

Assam Bora rice was sourced directly from local farmers in the Dibrugarh region of Upper Assam, India. Ferrous sulfate and anhydrous ferric chloride (FeCl_3) were obtained from Chemical store, India. Sodium hydroxide flakes (NaOH), monochloroacetic acid, glacial acetic acid, and ammonium hydroxide solution (25% v/v) were procured from Anuradha pharmacy college chikhli, India. Other chemical from local store potassium dihydrogen phosphate, disodium hydrogen phosphate (anhydrous), ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) disodium salt, and sodium chloride.

Fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, India. Methanol (95% v/v), isopropyl alcohol (99% v/v), and hydrochloric acid (HCl) were supplied by leben life science, Akola. Normal saline (sodium chloride injection IP, 0.9% w/v) was obtained from medical store. Throughout all experimental procedures, double-distilled water (DDW) prepared in-house was used. Unless otherwise stated, all chemicals and reagents employed in the study were of analytical grade and used without further purification.

2) Synthesis of carboxymethyl Assam Bora rice starch (CM-ABRS)

Carboxymethylation of Assam Bora rice starch was carried out following the principles of Williamson ether synthesis (Kost and Shefer, 1990). The native starch was suspended in isopropanol to form a slurry, which was then treated with 8N sodium hydroxide and chloroacetic acid (used as the etherifying agent). The reaction was maintained at 65 °C with continuous stirring at 2000 rpm to ensure uniform mixing and efficient substitution. The reaction proceeded for 3 hours, after which the resulting product was filtered and washed multiple times with 85% (v/v) ethanol until the filtrate reached a neutral pH (approximately pH 7), indicating removal of residual reagents and byproducts. To determine the amount of unreacted sodium hydroxide, a back-titration was performed. A 25 mL aliquot of the reaction mixture was titrated against 0.05 M hydrochloric acid using phenolphthalein as an indicator, as described in earlier studies and further referenced in Section [X] (Korhonen et al., 2000). This titration helped in estimating the degree of substitution indirectly and confirmed the completion of the etherification reaction.

3) Formulation of pristine magnetite (SPIONs)

An aqueous suspension of magnetite nanoparticles (SPIONs) was prepared using a co-precipitation method, as adapted from Kim et al. (2003b). A mixture of anhydrous ferric chloride (FeCl_3) and ferrous sulfate heptahydrate ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) in a 2:1 molar ratio was dissolved in water and stirred continuously at 1500 rpm while maintaining the temperature between 60–65 °C. To this mixture, 10 mL of 0.1 M ammonium hydroxide (NH_4OH , pH 11–14) was added dropwise under constant agitation. The reaction was carried out under a nitrogen atmosphere to prevent oxidation, and continued for approximately 30 minutes, during which the solution gradually turned black, indicating the formation of magnetite (Fe_3O_4). Following synthesis, the magnetite nanoparticles were separated from the reaction mixture using magnetic decantation. The collected particles were washed three times with deoxygenated double-distilled water (DDW) to remove any unreacted ions or residual by-products, and then dried for further characterization.

4) Formulation of CM-ABRS coated SPIONS (CM-ABRS SPIONS)

CM-ABRS-coated superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) were synthesized using a chemical co-precipitation method, based on the procedure reported by Kim et al. (2003b), with modifications. Various concentrations of CM-ABRS (0.1–1.0% w/v) were prepared by dissolving the polymer in 20 mL of deoxygenated double-distilled water (DDW), followed by magnetic stirring at room temperature for 30 minutes to ensure complete dissolution. Separately, a solution

containing Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions in a 1:1 molar ratio was prepared. To this iron precursor solution, 5 mL was added dropwise into the polymer solution under continuous stirring at 70–75 °C in a nitrogen atmosphere to prevent oxidation. The mixture was allowed to react for 30 minutes, during which a brown-colored complex of iron and the CM-ABRS polymer was formed. Subsequently, 10 mL of 0.1 M ammonium hydroxide solution was introduced slowly (dropwise) to the reaction mixture to raise the pH to 13, promoting the nucleation and formation of black magnetite nanoparticles (Gupta and Gupta, 2005b; Hong et al., 2004). The temperature of the reaction was then increased to 80 °C and maintained for 30 minutes, following an initial reaction period of 2.5 hours at 70–75 °C with continuous stirring at 2000 rpm to ensure effective coating and stabilization of SPIONs with CM-ABRS.

The resulting CM-ABRS SPION colloidal suspension was subjected to high-energy homogenization using a Silent Crusher S homogenizer (Heidolph Instruments GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). Homogenization was performed at various speeds and cycles to reduce particle size and improve uniformity. The influence of polymer concentration and homogenization parameters (speed and number of cycles) on particle size (Z-average) and polydispersity index (PDI) was systematically studied to identify optimal formulation conditions. After synthesis, the colloidal dispersion was washed thoroughly (3–4 times) with deoxygenated DDW (nitrogen bubbled) to remove unreacted ammonia and other residuals. The nanoparticles were then isolated by centrifugation at 14,500 rpm for 30 minutes at 4 °C. The resulting pellet was re-dispersed in 4–5 mL of deoxygenated DDW, followed by lyophilization using a freeze dryer (Labconco, USA) at –58.7 °C and 13 mTorr. Lyophilized CM-ABRS SPIONs were obtained without the use of any cryoprotectants (e.g., mannitol) and were used for all solid-state characterizations.

Results and discussion :

❖ Synthesis of Carboxymethyl Assam Bora-rice starch (CM-ABRS)

As outlined in our earlier study, the carboxymethylation of Assam Bora rice starch (ABRS) yielded carboxymethylated ABRS (CM-ABRS) with an optimal degree of substitution (DS) of 1.23. This was confirmed through spectroscopic analysis using Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H and ^{13}C NMR). According to Lawal (2004), this

chemical modification significantly alters the physicochemical properties of native ABRS—enhancing its solubility in cold water and improving powder flow characteristics.

The introduction of multiple carboxyl (–COOH) and hydroxyl (–OH) groups imparts a negative charge to CM-ABRS, making it a promising anionic carrier for drug delivery applications. Its anionic nature facilitates interaction with the positively charged iron species on the surface of magnetite (Fe₃O₄) nanoparticles. This interaction occurs via a Lewis acid-base mechanism, where the lone pair electrons from CM-ABRS coordinate with iron cations, aiding in the stable formation of coated superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) (Laurent et al., 2008).

❖ Formulation of CM-ABRS coated SPIONs (CM-ABRS-SPIONs)

Ferrous (Fe²⁺) and ferric (Fe³⁺) ions co-precipitate to generate CM-ABRS capped magnetite (Fe₃O₄) when dropwise additions of ammonia solution with a pH range of 9 to 14 are made (Si et al., 2004).

When 5 mL of the iron ion mixture (Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺) was added to 20 mL of the CM-ABRS solution, the reaction mixture gradually changed color from brown to orange, likely due to iron-induced crosslinking of the CM-ABRS polymer (Kim et al., 2003b). This mixture was then aged at 70–75 °C for 30 minutes. Subsequently, 10 mL of 0.1 M ammonium hydroxide was added dropwise to initiate magnetite precipitation. After maintaining the reaction at 75 °C with optimal stirring for 2.5 hours, black magnetite nanoparticles were successfully formed (Laurent et al., 2008). Excess ammonia was removed by heating the mixture at 80 °C for approximately 30 minutes. The superparamagnetic nature of the synthesized magnetite (illustrated in Fig. 4.3(A)) was confirmed by applying an external magnetic field using a tabletop NdFeB magnet, where the magnetic responsiveness was observed. This was further validated through vibrating sample magnetometry (VSM), which demonstrated the movement of the black magnetite particles in response to the magnetic field, confirming their magnetic properties. Maintaining an inert atmosphere during synthesis allows precise control over the nucleation rate and particle size distribution by regulating the critical oxidation steps involved in magnetite formation (Si et al., 2004). Additionally, a homogenizer was utilized to apply high mechanical energy and sonic cavitation, further reducing and homogenizing the size of the SPIONs (Anwar et al., 2011; Mallick et al., 2016b). For long-

term stability and ease of handling, the CM-ABRS coated SPIONs were lyophilized in the presence of 5% (w/v) mannitol as a cryoprotectant, which was used for subsequent studies (Fig. 4.3(C)). However, all solid-state characterizations were performed on lyophilized CM-ABRS SPIONs prepared without mannitol to avoid any interference.

➤ **Effect of the homogenization :**

The impact of homogenization speed on particle size was evaluated by varying the speed from 15,000 rpm to 35,000 rpm while keeping the number of homogenization cycles constant at one cycle of 1.5 minutes, as summarized in Table [X]. Increasing the homogenization speed from 15,000 rpm to 25,000 rpm led to a significant reduction in particle size, from 421.3 ± 4.82 nm down to 293.7 ± 6.58 nm (Mallick et al., 2016b). Although further increasing the speed to 35,000 rpm supplied higher mechanical energy—expected to reduce particle size even more (Asua, 2002)—no additional significant decrease was observed. Subsequently, the effect of homogenization cycles was optimized by varying the number of cycles from 1 to 3 while maintaining a constant speed of 25,000 rpm (Table [X]). This adjustment resulted in a sharp decline in particle size from 293.7 ± 6.58 nm to 203.7 ± 1.09 nm, attributed to improved homogenization efficiency, which facilitates better energy utilization for size reduction.

However, further increasing the number of cycles from 3 to 5 did not yield any meaningful decrease in particle size. Instead, it led to a higher polydispersity index (PDI) and a broader particle size distribution, as shown in Fig. 4.4(A). This effect is likely due to polymer detachment from the surface of the SPIONs caused by the excessive mechanical energy. Therefore, the optimal homogenization conditions for producing smaller, more uniform CM-ABRS SPIONs were established as 25,000 rpm and 3 cycles (Fig. [X]).

Table 4.2. Effect of homogenization process variables on particle size and PDI**Effect of homogenization speed :**

Sample ID	Homogenization variables Speed (rpm)	Z; average +/- S D No.ofcycles	(nm)	PDI +/- SD
CM-ABRS	15,000	1	420.2 +/- 4.76	0.301 +/- 0.012
SPIONS	20,000	1	312.6 +/- 416	0.383 +/- 0.051
0.8% (w/v)	25,000	1	291.3 +/- 6.42	1.336 +/- 0.094

Effect of homogenization Cycles :

Sample ID	Homogenization variables Speed (rpm)	Z; average +/- S D No.ofcycles	(nm)	PDI +/- SD
CM-ABRS	25,000	2	237.2 +/- 1.39	0.074 +/- 0.023
SPIONS				
0.8% (w/v)	25,000	3	199.5 +/- 1.06	0.025 +/- 0.003

Values of the Z-average and PDI represent the mean \pm SD (n=3).

➤ **Morphology: Transmission electron microscopy :**

The Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis showed that the uncoated SPIONs were well-defined, spherical, and had a compact texture, with particle sizes below 10 nm, as illustrated in Fig. 4.5(A). In contrast, the CM-ABRS-coated SPIONs (0.8% w/v) exhibited spherical

morphology with an average diameter of approximately 200 nm (Fig. 4.5(B)). The observed clustering of CM-ABRS SPIONs is likely due to interactions between hydroxyl and carboxyl functional groups on adjacent particles. TEM results indicated that the hydrodynamic sizes measured by dynamic light scattering (DLS) corresponded to these aggregated clusters rather than to individual nanoparticle dimensions (Jain et al., 2008b). Due to the high molecular weight of CM-ABRS (~90 kDa), multiple SPION cores can be encapsulated within a single cluster (Amstad et al., 2011). This interpretation aligns with findings from Sun et al. (Xie et al., 2007), who reported that SPIONs dispersed in aqueous media are surrounded by an extended layer of hydrated polymer ligands.

Figure 4.5. TEM micrograph of: (A) Pristine magnetite (B) CM-ABRS SPIONs.

➤ **Interaction of magnetite with CM-ABRS: FTIR analysis :**

The interaction between pure magnetite and CM-ABRS in the final CM-ABRS SPIONs formulation was investigated using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). The FTIR spectra of pure magnetite, CM-ABRS, and CM-ABRS SPIONs (0.8% w/v) are presented in Figures 4.6(A), (B), and (C), respectively. For pure magnetite, the broad absorption band observed at 3253 cm^{-1} corresponds to O–H stretching vibrations, while the band at 1625 cm^{-1} is attributed

to bending vibrations of water molecules adsorbed on the surface of iron oxide nanoparticles (Smith, 1979). Additionally, characteristic peaks at 630 cm^{-1} and 541 cm^{-1} are assigned to the $\text{Fe}^{\text{Th}}\text{-O-Fe}^{\text{Oh}}$ stretching vibrations, where Fe^{Th} and Fe^{Oh} denote iron ions located in tetrahedral and octahedral sites within the magnetite crystal lattice.

In the CM-ABRS spectrum, a prominent peak around 3391 cm^{-1} corresponds to O–H stretching vibrations, indicative of hydroxyl groups. The presence of the carboxymethyl group in CM-ABRS is confirmed by distinctive peaks at 1597 cm^{-1} and 1422 cm^{-1} , representing the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the carboxylate ($-\text{COO}^-$) groups, respectively, as reported by Mohapatra et al. (2017).

Figure. FT-IR spectra of : (A) Pristine magnetite

(B) CM-ABRS

(C) CM-ABRS SPIONS

In the FTIR spectrum of CM-ABRS SPIONS, the absorption band observed at 2033 cm^{-1} is likely attributable to C–H stretching vibrations, while the broad peak near 3364 cm^{-1} corresponds to O–H stretching. Notably, distinct peaks at 1596 cm^{-1} and 1401 cm^{-1} confirm the successful attachment of CM-ABRS chains to the magnetite nanoparticle surface. Compared to the unmodified CM-ABRS—where carboxylate asymmetric and symmetric stretching appear at 1597 cm^{-1} and 1422 cm^{-1} , respectively—these peaks exhibit a slight blue shift upon binding to magnetite. This shift is probably due to a reduction in the conjugation of the carboxylate (COO^-)

groups upon surface coordination, which lowers the effective force constant, in agreement with previous reports (Si et al., 2004). The free carboxylate exhibits partial double-bond character in the C–O bond, resulting in a higher force constant and thus requiring absorption at higher wavenumbers.

Additionally, a broad absorption band at 3134 cm^{-1} appears in the CM-ABRS SPIONs spectrum but is absent in pure magnetite. This band is likely associated with the O–H stretching vibrations of carboxylic acid groups, as noted in earlier studies (Hussain et al., 2005; Sun et al., 2010). The presence of CM-ABRS on the magnetite surface is further supported by characteristic absorption peaks at 619 cm^{-1} and 576 cm^{-1} , which are attributed to $\text{Fe}^{\text{T}}\text{–O–Fe}^{\text{O}}\text{H}$ stretching vibrations within the magnetite lattice. These peaks suggest bonding interactions between CM-ABRS and magnetite, possibly via hydrogen bonding or coordination mechanisms (Li et al., 2004; Zhang et al., 2003).

CONCLUSION :

In this study firstly focused on the developed and characterized of stable superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) coated with carboxymethyl Assam Bora rice starch (CM-ABRS) at a concentration of 0.8% (w/v). Their in vitro localization capability was assessed in a model system consisting of FITC-labeled red blood cells (RBCs) suspended at a hematocrit of 45% within a square glass capillary channel (cross-sectional area: $500 \times 500\ \mu\text{m}^2$), simulating targeted drug delivery conditions. Based on our simulation studies, CM-ABRS SPIONs do not appear to impede blood flow in capillaries over extended periods, which is promising for various therapeutic and theranostic applications. However, the continued aggregation observed after 600 seconds warrants further investigation to understand the potential risk of capillary blockage during in vivo use, particularly in contexts such as magnetic drug targeting or magnetic hyperthermia.

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